

EFFECTS OF CORROSION ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF STEEL BARS

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Syed Amir Sohail**Abstract**

Corrosion is the basic problem of deteriorating all steel structures due to environmental conditions and chemical reactions. This leads structures to failures, which have significant economic losses and negative environmental effects. This study aims to investigate the effects of corrosion on the mechanical properties of steel bars. A comparative experimental design is used, which has seven steps, including problem definition, parameter identification, sample preparation, data collection, data analysis, results, and conclusion. This experimental design analyzed data by comparing the mechanical properties of corroded steel bars to international standards such as the American Society of Testing and Materials (ASTM), the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), and Pakistani Standards (PS). Moreover, calculating the coefficient of variation of all parameters helps in data consistency and reliability. The results showed that corrosion has severe effects on the mechanical properties of steel by leading steel bars to degradation and increasing the risk of failure. Due to corrosion, the yield strength is decreased by 17.62%, the ultimate strength is reduced by 20.19%, the tensile strength is decreased by 27.52%, the percentage elongation is decreased by 15.76%, and the nominal diameter is decreased by 6.62%. This research highlights how mechanical properties are degraded due to corrosion, which undermines the structural integrity, safety, and durability of steel-reinforced structures.

INTRODUCTION

The earliest production of steel began in 1800 BC in the South Asian subcontinent, ancient India [1]. In this period, a process was developed for the melting of carbon-rich metals and iron. This process produced steel with high strength and durability by adding carbon to iron [1]. The Middle East and Mediterranean (Romans and Greeks) valued Indian

steel for its good mechanical properties [2]. They used it for making high-quality swords and armor. In East Asia, the production of steel began in China around 600 BC. They used a method called finery forge for the melting of steel and its production [3]. To produce steel, the Chinese combined coal and iron. During this period, the production of steel

became common and spread to other parts of Asia and Europe. In the beginning, the production was quite difficult and laborious, needing more labor and time. However, with time, the process and production techniques are modified for better results.

During the Middle Ages, new tools and techniques were introduced, which made production more efficient than in the past. A process, finery forge, developed by the Chinese around 600 BC, was widespread in Europe and was an efficient method than the Indian method [3]. In Japan, the Japanese produced high-carbon steel, which was very durable in properties. Steelmakers in Japan introduced and developed new techniques and methods to produce steel, such as hammering and folding [4]. Continuous improvements were made with time, such as the development of low-carbon steel and then high-carbon steel, which played an important role in the arms industry.

In the 18th century, the Industrial Revolution was a turning point in the mass production of steel, by the development of new tools, techniques, processes, and technologies [5]. The development of the Bessemer process in 1850 was the first step towards mass production [6]. In the late 19th century, the Open Hearth Furnace (OHF) further improved the production of steel [7]. At the beginning of the 20th century, stainless steel was developed, with improved quality and properties [8]. New applications of steel were expanded by using steel in construction, industries, vehicles, and transportation. Contemporary steel has very advanced mechanical properties.

There are four types of steel based on the percentage composition of iron, carbon, and other elements [9]. The common types of steel are (i) Carbon Steel, (ii) Stainless Steel, (iii) Alloy Steel, and (iv) High Strength Steel [9]. Each type is further subdivided into two or three subtypes. Carbon steel has three subtypes such as (i) high carbon steel having 1.4% carbon and 1% manganese [10]. (ii) Medium carbon steel, which has 0.6% carbon and 1% manganese. (iii) Low-carbon steel, which has 0.3% carbon and 0.7% manganese [10].

Stainless Steel has further three subtypes based on the percentage composition of chromium and carbon, such as (i) Martensite Stainless Steel, which

has 17% chromium and 1% carbon [11]. (ii) Ferrite Stainless Steel has 17% chromium and 0.1% carbon. (iii) Austenite Stainless Steel has 20% chromium, 12% nickel, and 0.1% carbon [11].

The third type of steel is Alloy Steel, which has three types composed of molybdenum, carbon, and chromium in different percentages [12]. They are (i) Molybdenum Carbon Steel, composed of 5% molybdenum and 1% carbon [12]. (ii) Nickel Chromium Steel is composed of 2% chromium, 2% nickel, and 1% carbon. (iii) Chromium Steel is composed of 1% carbon and 2% chromium [12].

The fourth type of steel is high-carbon steel, which is a composition of carbon and alloying metals with iron. It has two subtypes such as (i) Dual Phase Steel and (ii) High Strength Low Alloy Steel [13].

Corrosion is one of the costliest problems faced by the whole world. In the modern world, corrosion still widely affects the industrial sector, transportation sector, and construction area, which leads to the failure of structures by degradation of the mechanical properties of steel bars [14]. This has very catastrophic effects on human beings in the form of loss of lives and casualties, on the environment in the form of the creation of wastes, and on the economy in the form of loss of wealth and assets [15]. For the prevention of corrosion, different industries made dyes and coatings, laboratories of material science made advancements in steel structures and resistance, and corrosion is still a big problem for the world and requires major concern to overcome this giant problem [14].

Literature Review

Corrosion affects several materials, which include alloys, metals, and the composition of metallic and non-metallic elements. Corrosion is a complex problem for many industries, such as manufacturing industries, oil and gas industries, the construction sector, and the transportation sector. It plays a key role in the failure of structures, which is a risk to human life, damages the environment, and is a loss to the economy. Corrosion has deep effects on society, the environment, the economy, materials, and the strength of structures [15].

Corrosion has a direct effect on society in the form of the failure of structures [16]. Human beings live in buildings, palaces, and houses and use bridges for

movement and transportation. With all the structures, humans have a direct relationship. Its failures cause casualties and fatal accidents, due to which displacement of people occurs [15].

Corrosion affects the environment due to the creation of waste from corroded steel. Pakistan produced 1.5 million tons of the waste of corroded steel in 2022. In 2023, the production of scrap increased by 15%, and the waste of corroded steel reached 1.8 million tons, while for the year 2024, the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics forecasted 2.2 million tons of waste production [17]. The pipes that are used for the transportation of oil in seas and oceans are severely affected by corrosion, which is the cause of failures, creates leaks, and pollutes the aquatic ecosystem. Oil spills have shocking effects on marine (aquatic) life. Corrosion is the cause of leakages in the tanks, especially when chemicals are stored, which have hazardous effects on the environment by contaminating water and soil.

As corrosion has social and environmental effects, in the same way, it has economic effects as well [18]. Due to corrosion, the lifespan of the steel bars

decreases, which directly reduces the lifespan of the structures [16]. To overcome corrosion, several types of coatings or dyes are used to cover the steel, provide resistance to corrosion, or slow down the rate of corrosion. In America, the annual cost of corrosion calculated by the National Association of Corrosion Engineers is more than 267 billion dollars, which is more than a country's economy [19]. In Europe, the annual cost of corrosion calculated by the European Federation of Corrosion is more than 200 billion dollars [20].

We computed effective diameter from mass-loss measurements. For a specimen of length L and density ρ ,

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{4m}{\pi\rho L}} \quad (1)$$

If using mass per unit length w : $d = \sqrt{(4w / (\pi\rho))}$ (1a)

All variables are reported with SI units and measurement uncertainties (scale and length)

Figure 1: Effect of Corrosion on Steel Bars

Ignasi et al. studied the effects of corrosion on the mechanical properties of steel. To analyze the effects of corrosion on steel, more than 180 corroded steel samples were tested. On 140 steel samples, fatigue tests were performed, while on the remaining 40 samples of steel, monotonic tests were performed. The results showed a non-linear severe reduction in the mechanical properties due to corrosion. The research concluded that corrosion has an inverse relation with the mechanical properties of steel [23].

Xiaoyan et al. evaluated the effects of non-uniform corrosion on the mechanical properties of steel. The study showed that the size and depth of the pits increase when the rate of corrosion increases. On the other hand, the cross-sectional area and average mass of the steel bars also decrease. This research shows that corrosion has a direct relation with the formation of pits, size, and depth of pits, and has an inverse relation with the cross-sectional area and average mass of steel bars. The results showed that

ultimate strength, ductility, and yield strength decrease with the increase in corrosion. The observation and analysis showed that pits are present in the weakest location of steel bars [24].

Wang et al. used a random field model to investigate corrosion and its effects on the mechanical properties of steel. From the study, the relationship between corrosion and mechanical properties was found. Results showed a negative relationship between corrosion and the properties of steel. Yield strength, tensile strength, elastic modulus, and all other parameters deteriorate linearly with the increase in corrosion [25].

Francois et al. took 27-year-old steel bars from beams that were open to chloride surroundings. All the tested bars had a non-uniform degree of corrosion and pits. The results showed that the mechanical properties, especially ultimate stress and ultimate strain, were affected by corrosion. Moreover, ultimate elongation decreased, while true yield strength remained constant [26].

Xuanyi et al. investigated the effects of corrosion on the mechanical properties of high steel. High steel is used in structures due to its good performance. The steel was corroded through an electrochemical-accelerated-corrosion test. As the rate of corrosion increases, it is distributed over the steel bars unevenly. Yield strength, ultimate strength, ultimate strain, and modulus of elasticity decreased with the increase in corrosion. Moreover, the effects of non-uniform corrosion are more than the effects of uniform corrosion on steel bars [27].

Most available studies are on samples that were corroded in less than three years. Very few studies

have investigated the effects of corrosion on the mechanical properties of steel, which corrodes for a long time, 10 to 60 years [28]. Apostolopoulos et al. investigated the consequences of corrosion on ductility of steel. Furthermore, seismic activities and environmental conditions reduce the lifespan and durability of steel. First, it leads steel to corrosion, then increases its rate by the process of chlorine penetration and carbonation. Therefore, it is very difficult to find the service life of steel in a structure. No model can analyze it logically. This research shows that as the corrosion exposure duration increases, steel loses its mass rapidly along with the decrease in cross-sectional area. It results in the decrease of nominal diameter and tensile ductility of steel bars [29].

Methodology

Research methodology plays a vital role in the undertaking of research. It is comprised of many steps which affect the design, goals, and success of a study. Good research methodology will enable the researcher to solve the problem, get conclusions from the results, and make a better way of decision [30]. The methodology shown in Figure 2 includes a problem statement, identification of parameters, and preparation of samples, data collection, data analysis, results, and conclusion.

Tensile tests were carried out on a calibrated universal testing machine (UTM) in accordance with ASTM E8/E8M. Strain was recorded using an axial extensometer over the specified gauge length, and a constant crosshead speed was applied to maintain a quasi-static initial strain rate.

Figure 2: Adopted Methodology for this Research

After a comprehensive literature review, it is implored that corrosion severely affects the mechanical properties of steel. Researchers have found the effects of corrosion, but in most cases, the samples under consideration were for less than three years. As discussed in the previous section, life span and environment are critical for corrosion, In this research, 45 to 50-year-old steel samples from an old demolished bridge in Peshawar are considered.

The second step involves parameter selection. The yield strength, ultimate strength, tensile strength, elongation, percentage elongation, nominal diameter, effective diameter, and bending are the most common parameters [31]. This research also considers these parameters.

In the third step, the samples were prepared according to international standards such as the American Society of Testing and Materials (ASTM), the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), and Pakistani Standards [33]. The standard length of samples for tensile tests is 203.2 millimeters. The standard sample size for one ton of steel is 3 to 5 samples according to ASTM E8/E8M-21 and ISO 6892-1:2019 [32]. As per the standards, the sample size for mild steel is 3 to 5, for high steel, it is 5 to 7, and for alloy steel, it is 5 to 10 samples [33]. For better and more accurate results, the sample

size for this research is 15 samples, which is higher than the required sample size.

After selecting the samples, the tensile and bending tests were performed on two sets of 15 samples. Percent elongation is calculated through tensile tests, yield strength, ultimate strength, tensile strength, and elongation. Nominal diameters are measured through a vernier caliper, while effective diameters through equation (i), where W is weight ρ is density. Moreover, three-point bending tests were also done, and the cracks were observed through the naked eye.

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{4m}{\pi\rho L}} \tag{1}$$

If using mass per unit length w : $d = \sqrt{(4 w / (\pi \rho))}$ (1a)

After testing and data collection, it is analyzed and compared with the existing international standards. The comparison is necessary for data reliability and consistency. After reliability, the results are visualized and explained through graphs. The effects of corrosion on the mechanical properties are presented as a percent reduction. This shows the relationship between corrosion and its mechanical properties.

In the last step, the conclusion, key aspects of this research are highlighted. The design and method

which is followed in this research are summarized in this step.

Data Collection and Analysis

The samples are tested and compared to ensure consistency. The coefficient of variation (CV) is used to confirm the consistency. CV is calculated by finding the mean and standard deviation of the samples. The standard deviation is divided by the mean, then multiplied by 100. When the coefficient of variation is less than 5%, it shows that the data are close to the mean and indicates high precision with minimum error and low variability. It shows reliability and closeness, better repeatability, and high confidence [35].

The mean of the yield strength is 49.43, while its standard deviation is 1.7594, and its coefficient of variation (CV) is 3.56% given in table 1, which shows a high level of consistency and precision

between the yield strength of all the samples. The CV of ultimate strength is 4.19% given in table 2, the CV of tensile strength is 3.97% in table 3, nominal diameter is 1.84% given in table 5, and percentage elongation is 14.61%, given in table 4, which shows that all the data are close to their mean, while the CV value of percentage elongation is high due to systematic error in transducer, which calculated the elongation.. It shows precision with the least random error and very trivial variability with high confidence.

Figure 3 shows the yield strength and average yield strength of corroded old steel bars, with low variability and high consistency. It has a standard deviation of 1.76, which shows less dispersion and high precision. The data values are concentrated near the mean value, showing a slight spread.

Figure 3: Yield strength and average yield strength of corroded steel bars

Table 1: Yield strength, its average, standard deviation, error margin and coefficient of variation (%).

Samples	Yield Strength (Ksi)	Average Yield Strength (Mean)	Standard Deviation	Error Margin	Coefficient of Variation (%)
1	46.42	49.43	1.7594	-1.71	3.5594
2	46.94	49.43	1.7594	-1.42	
3	47.41	49.43	1.7594	-1.15	
4	48.38	49.43	1.7594	-0.60	
5	49.78	49.43	1.7594	0.20	
6	50.49	49.43	1.7594	0.60	
7	51.33	49.43	1.7594	1.08	
8	48.59	49.43	1.7594	-0.48	
9	48.69	49.43	1.7594	-0.42	
10	49.93	49.43	1.7594	0.28	
11	52.39	49.43	1.7594	1.68	

12	51.69	49.43	1.7594	1.28
13	49.83	49.43	1.7594	0.23
14	48.73	49.43	1.7594	-0.40
15	50.85	49.43	1.7594	0.81

Figure 4 shows the ultimate strength of all samples and their average. The average ultimate strength of the corroded old steel bar is 63.85 ksi, while its standard deviation is 2.68, and the coefficient of

variation is 4.19% given in table 2, which indicates high precision and low variability between data and shows accurate measurement. The error margin is also very small, ranges from -1.46 to +1.46.

Figure 4: Ultimate strength and average ultimate strength of corroded steel bars

Table 2: Ultimate strength, its average, standard deviation, error margin and coefficient of variation (%).

Ultimate Strength (Ksi)	Average Ultimate Strength	Standard Deviation	Error Margin	Coefficient of Variation (%)
60.42	63.85	2.6776	-1.28	4.1936
61.55	63.85	2.6776	-0.86	
61.42	63.85	2.6776	-0.91	
65.28	63.85	2.6776	0.53	
62.73	63.85	2.6776	-0.42	
65.39	63.85	2.6776	0.58	
66.09	63.85	2.6776	0.84	
62.91	63.85	2.6776	-0.35	
65.67	63.85	2.6776	0.68	
62.51	63.85	2.6776	-0.50	
67.73	63.85	2.6776	1.45	
66.87	63.85	2.6776	1.13	
61.42	63.85	2.6776	-0.91	
59.93	63.85	2.6776	-1.46	
67.76	63.85	2.6776	1.46	

Figure 5 shows the tensile strength and average tensile strength of corroded old steel bars and their

distribution around the mean. The mean of tensile strength is 57.98 ksi, while its standard deviation is

2.30, which shows a small spread. The coefficient of variation is 3.97% given in table 3, which is very small and indicates less random error in

measurement with high precision and reliability. The error margin ranges from -1.68 to +1.43

Figure 5: Tensile strength and average tensile strength of corroded old steel bars

Table 3: Tensile strength, its average, standard deviation, error margin and coefficient of variation (%)

Tensile Strength (Ksi)	Average Tensile Strength (Ksi)	Standard Deviation	Error Margin	Coefficient of Variation (%)
54.13	57.98	2.2993	-1.68	3.9657
57.26	57.98	2.2993	-0.31	
56.54	57.98	2.2993	-0.62	
58.03	57.98	2.2993	0.02	
57.68	57.98	2.2993	-0.13	
59.11	57.98	2.2993	0.49	
60.08	57.98	2.2993	0.91	
56.48	57.98	2.2993	-0.65	
60.18	57.98	2.2993	0.96	
57.48	57.98	2.2993	-0.22	
60.88	57.98	2.2993	1.26	
61.28	57.98	2.2993	1.43	
55.27	57.98	2.2993	-1.18	
54.79	57.98	2.2993	-1.39	
60.57	57.98	2.2993	1.13	

Figure 5 shows the percentage elongation and average percentage elongation of corroded old steel bars having an average equal to 10.11 while the standard deviation is 1.48 given in table 4, which shows a very close distribution around the mean. Its

CV is equal to 14.61%, which shows that the data have some variability. The standard deviation is low, while the coefficient of variation is moderate, which shows that the data is consistent. The error margins ranges from -1.77 to +1.62.

Figure 6: Percentage elongation and average percentage elongation of corroded steel bars

Table 4: Percentage elongation, its average, standard deviation, error margin and coefficient of variation (%).

Percentage Elongation	Average Percentage Elongation	Standard Deviation	Error Margin	Coefficient of Variation (%)
11.63	10.11	1.4767	1.03	14.60587174
7.50	10.11	1.4767	-1.77	
8.62	10.11	1.4767	-1.01	
12.50	10.11	1.4767	1.62	
8.75	10.11	1.4767	-0.92	
10.63	10.11	1.4767	0.35	
10.00	10.11	1.4767	-0.07	
11.38	10.11	1.4767	0.86	
9.13	10.11	1.4767	-0.67	
8.75	10.11	1.4767	-0.92	
11.25	10.11	1.4767	0.77	
9.13	10.11	1.4767	-0.67	
11.13	10.11	1.4767	0.69	
9.38	10.11	1.4767	-0.50	
11.88	10.11	1.4767	1.20	

Table 5: Nominal diameter, its average, standard deviation, error margin and coefficient of variation

Nominal Diameter (mm)	Average Diameter (mm)	Standard Deviation	Error Margin	Coefficient of Variation (%)
11.30	11.21	0.2063	0.44	1.8399
10.90	11.21	0.2063	-1.50	
11.10	11.21	0.2063	-0.53	
11.10	11.21	0.2063	-0.53	
10.89	11.21	0.2063	-1.55	
11.20	11.21	0.2063	-0.05	
11.30	11.21	0.2063	0.44	
11.40	11.21	0.2063	0.92	
11.50	11.21	0.2063	1.41	
11.40	11.21	0.2063	0.92	

11.30	11.21	0.2063	0.44
11.10	11.21	0.2063	-0.53
10.90	11.21	0.2063	-1.50
11.50	11.21	0.2063	1.41
11.20	11.21	0.2063	-0.05

Results and Discussion

Yield strength defines the elastic limit of a material. After yield strength, plastic deformation starts and cannot return to its original shape. Within the elastic limit, not crossing the yield point, steel can regain its original shape and deform permanently. Figure 7 shows the yield strength and average of corroded old steel samples. Blue dots represent the yield strength of all the samples, spread above and below the average line. The above two lines, gray and orange, represent the international standard limits of yield strength, which are the upper and lower limits. For grade 60, having a nominal diameter of 12-13

millimeters, the minimum yield strength is 60 ksi. This figure shows that the data is consistent, but it is not as per the standards. Corrosion has reduced the nominal diameter, pitting has created localized weaknesses, due to which the corroded old steel loses its yield strength and deforms easily, losing its ability to withstand high loads. Due to corrosion and the creation of pits, the minimum reduction in yield strength is 12.68%, while the maximum reduction in yield strength is 22.63%. On average, the yield strength of corroded old steel samples is deteriorate by 17.62%.

Figure 7: Standard limits of yield strength, yield strength, and average yield strength

Ultimate strength is the ultimate tensile strength, which is the maximum bearing capacity of steel without failing and breaking. Ultimate strength shows the maximum ability of steel to extreme loads and stresses. Corrosion has a direct relation with ultimate strength, it reduces ultimate strength by decreasing the diameter of bars, creating pits, which leads steel to Embrittlement. Figure 8 shows the ultimate and average ultimate strength of all the corroded old steel samples, along with standard

upper and lower limits of ultimate strength. The blue dots represent the ultimate strength of all the corroded samples, distributed above and below a green line, which represents the average ultimate strength of all the samples. The data shows consistency but is not within the standard limits. The maximum reduction that in the ultimate strength of is 25.09 %, while the minimum reduction is 15.30 %. The average, ultimate strength reduces by 20.19

Figure 8: Standard limits of ultimate strength, ultimate strength, and average ultimate strength

The change in length of a steel bar due to the application of a load is elongation. While strain is the ratio of change in length per unit of original length. Elongation tells about the brittleness and ductility of a material due to its specific ranges for all materials. Figure 9 shows the percentage and average percentage elongation along with its upper and lower standard limits, which are 12 % and 20 %. The blue dots show the percentage elongation of all the corroded old steel samples distributed above and

below the average line. There is one blue dot, sample 4, which follows the standard lower limit of percentage elongation, while the remaining samples are not as per the standards, showing degradation in percentage elongation due to corrosion and pitting. The maximum reduction in percentage elongation is 37.05%, while the minimum reduction is 1.04%. On average, the percentage elongation of corroded old steel bars reduces by 15.76%.

Figure 9: Standard limits of percentage elongation, percentage elongation, and average percentage

Tensile strength is an important property of steel, which is the ratio of ultimate strength and strain. There are three cases of tensile strength and ultimate strength: (i) When tensile strength is greater than ultimate strength, it is not possible. (ii) When tensile strength is less than ultimate strength, it is a normal case. (iii) When tensile strength is equal to ultimate strength, it is a unique case. The second case is the best because there is a difference between tensile strength and ultimate strength, which indicates failure before permanent failure. Figure 10 shows the tensile strength and average tensile strength of the corroded old steel bars, along with upper and lower

standard limits. The blue dots distributed above and below a blue average line show the tensile strength of the corroded old steel bars. The gray and orange lines represent standard lower and upper limits. All the samples are outside the standard limits, which shows a reduction in tensile strength due to corrosion and pitting. The lower standard limit is 80 ksi, while the upper limit is 105 ksi. The maximum reduction noted in the corroded old steel bars is 32.34%, while the minimum reduction that is noted is 23.40%. On average, tensile strength is 27.52% decreased due to severe effects of corrosion.

Figure 10: Tensile strength (UTS) of corroded bars, mean with 95% CI and applicable standard limits.

Table 6 summaries all the results and shows that the mechanical properties that are affected due to corrosion, its percentage reduction, negative or positive effect, and the standard limits of steel.

Table 6: Percentage reduction in the mechanical properties of steel.

Mechanical Properties	Corroded Old Steel	Standard Limits	Effect of Corrosion	Negative or Positive Effect	Percentage Reduction
Yield Strength	49.43 Ksi	60 Ksi	Effectuated	Decreased	17.62%
Ultimate Strength	63.85 Ksi	80-130 Ksi	Effectuated	Decreased	20.19%
Tensile Strength	57.98 Ksi	80-105 Ksi	Effectuated	Decreased	27.52%

Percentage Elongation	10.11 %	12-20 %	Effectuated	Decreased	15.76%
Nominal Diameter	11.21 mm	12-13 mm	Effectuated	Decreased	6.62%

Conclusion

For the investigation of the effects of corrosion on the mechanical properties of steel, a robust methodology is employed. 50 years old steel bars are identified and analyzed. The samples are analyzed and investigated, and reliability is checked through the coefficient of variation. In the sixth and seventh steps, results and conclusions are explained. In the present investigation, the effects of corrosion on the mechanical properties of grade 60 steel bars are examined. When testing is performed on corroded old steel bars, it shows that corrosion and pitting severely affect the mechanical properties of steel, subjected for a long time to environmental conditions, chemical reactions, and physical stresses. From the above study, it is noted that corrosion, along with pitting, has a negative relation with the mechanical properties of steel. Due to corrosion, the yield strength is decreased by 17.62%, the ultimate strength is decreased by 20.19%, the tensile strength is decreased by 27.52%, the percentage elongation is decreased by 15.76%, and the nominal diameter is decreased by 6.62%.

This paper reports the effects of atmospheric and pitting corrosion on the mechanical properties of 45-50 years old steel bars. Experimental results of tensile and bending tests which are carried out on naturally corroded steel bars. Relations between corrosion and loss of mechanical properties such as yield strength, ultimate strength, tensile strength, percentage elongation and nominal diameter of steel are presented in this paper. The finding of this study highlights the importance of considering the atmospheric and pitting corrosion when designing and maintaining steel structures. The results of this study can be used for more effective corrosion approaches and developments to improve the durability of steel structures. Future research should focus on investigating the corrosion behavior of steel bars exposed to different environmental conditions and developing more effective corrosion protection methods. Ultimately this study demonstrates the need for a more comprehensive understanding of the

corrosion behavior of steel bars in harsh environments and highlights the importance of continued research in this area.

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